

How tech companies should filter ideas submitted by users using money as a tool (Extended)

Abstract: The concept presented suggests a method for tech companies to filter ideas submitted by users using a payment-based system as a tool for prioritization. This proposal aims to address the challenge companies face in sorting through a multitude of ideas, providing a framework where individuals can self-filter their submissions based on payment levels.

The idea suggests four levels of payment options for idea submission to a tech company.

1. **For Free:** Ideas can be submitted for free, but there's no secure channel or guaranteed attention for the proposal within the company.
2. **Small Fee:** Submission involves paying a small fee, increasing the likelihood of the idea being heard by someone within the company.
3. **Medium Fee:** A higher payment ensures the idea reaches a key person within the company who can assess and value it more thoroughly.
4. **Large Fee:** The highest payment level guarantees that the idea is directly reviewed by the CEO of the company.

Conclusion: This payment-based system allows the company to distribute ideas more fairly, essentially providing a pay-to-view scheme. Submitters purchase the company's "attention" through payments, allowing their projects to be heard and reviewed accordingly.

While this proposal suggests a way to streamline idea submissions, it raises ethical considerations. The idea of pay-to-view schemes might lead to concerns about fairness and accessibility. Ideas might be evaluated based on financial capacity rather than merit, potentially limiting innovation from those who cannot afford higher payment tiers.

Additionally, such a system might incentivize prioritization of ideas based on financial gain rather than their intrinsic value or potential impact, potentially undermining the pursuit of groundbreaking concepts.

Overall, while the proposal introduces an intriguing concept of self-filtering ideas through a payment-based system, it brings forth ethical considerations that would need careful evaluation before implementation.

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